

Learners' Struggles and Coping in Printed Modular Learning Modality

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Abstract:

The study used a mixed-methods design to explore learners' struggles and coping levels in the printed modular learning modality in La Libertad II district, employing a validated and reliable self-made questionnaire. Data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, means, and the Mann-Whitney U Test with descriptive and comparative analysis. Most learners were female, from larger families earning above Php10,000, and living far from school. Learners' coping was moderate in accomplishing learning tasks but high in managing the learning environment, multitasking, and time management. No significant differences in coping levels were found when grouped by demographic variables. Key struggles included difficulty with independent learning, home distractions, multiple responsibilities, and unguided activity schedules. Recommendations emphasize involving parents during School Monitoring Evaluation and Adjustments (SMEA) to discuss and address these challenges, reminding them that the home serves as the learning environment during weekdays and encouraging adherence to school-provided schedules. Additionally, schools should limit costly activities, and teacher advisers are encouraged to modify modules to reduce financial burdens on families.

Keywords: Learning Environment, Modular Learning, Monitoring Evaluation

Introduction:

The cancellation of classes due to the Covid-19 pandemic has intensified the struggles of the educational system, especially in the learning process (Dayagbil et al., 2021). The virus puts face-to-face learning on hold and has led the Department of Education (DepEd) to implement the Basic Education - Learning Continuity Plan. A framework that will ensure that the children are still learning in a safe environment through distance learning – a non-traditional approach where learners receive the instructions at home.

However, distance learning modality posed challenges, especially since most learners were used to traditional teaching. According to Castroverde and Acala (2021) on distance learning, the common challenges of the learners were struggling in accomplishing the learning tasks. This is rooted in the sudden shift of learning modality, which requires them to adjust to a new learning environment, do multiple tasks, and manage time. Hence, learners must develop strategies to make their learning meaningful at home. According to Guevarra and Cinames (2017), learners need to develop various coping strategies to manage stressful situations. Coping mechanisms are important in distance learning so that the learners can overcome the different struggles about accomplishing learning activities, learning environment, balancing tasks, and time management.

The printed modular learning model emerged as the most preferred teaching scheme for parents and learners during the pandemic (Dangle Y & Sumaoang J, 2020). During the first year of implementation, different issues were raised. In the research venue, in particular, the learners complained that there were plenty of tasks to be accomplished. They were often assigned house chores, making it difficult for them to work on their modular tasks. From informal interviews, it was found that there were learners who didn't take the modules seriously (Boholano et al., 2022). Others just copied the answer keys, and there were learners submitting unanswered modules. But despite these alarming circumstances, there were learners who showed a positive attitude. Few were seen diligently answering the activities at home, while some multi-tasking activities and even slept late to meet the deadline. These show that the learners have different struggles, attitudes, and coping strategies in the implementation of modular distance learning (Bacomo et al., 2022).

Considering the conditions stated above, the researcher, as a Grade 6 adviser, is motivated to conduct a study to uncover the different struggles of learners as they took on a different schooling approach and their coping mechanisms to be able to master and acquire learning during the printed modular learning modality.

Current State of Knowledge

Learners' Struggles in PMLM. According to Sullivan (2021), education can be a struggle for every learner to learn and think differently. When learning takes place in distance learning, learning becomes complicated. Since this is a new learning modality, learners face various struggles, especially when performing the learning tasks. Meanwhile, Guevarra and Cinames (2017) mentioned that it is important for learners to develop various coping strategies to manage stressful situations.

In addition, Mensah (2020) also mentioned that making printed distance learning work for all learners could be challenging. With many learners struggling to learn independently, generalizing distance learning to a single approach can be critical to the learning process. He asserted that it is only possible when there is equitable access to the materials, adequate preparation time, and training for teachers.

Furthermore, Amir (2020) pointed out several factors contributing to the struggles of learners during printed modular learning. These include external factors such as unstable internet connection, the extra financial burden of the internet quota, and internal factors such as time management and difficulty focusing.

Within a single district in the United States of America, teachers and parents have reported that some children were thriving with fewer social distractions or have been energized by their newfound independence. While some other families have parents who can oversee their children's remote learning, many youths care for younger siblings while their parents work for their essentials (Weir, 2020).

Meanwhile, Dickler (2021) reported that more than half of the public school teachers in California from kindergarten to senior high school considered the pandemic a significant learning loss for learners in academic and social-emotional progress. This means that more learners were struggling as the new learning modality was being utilized.

Jam-packed schedules were shown to be one of the significant factors adding to learners' struggles during printed modular learning. Learners who are over-committed, especially if they feel obligated to take certain courses or participate in activities, are more likely to experience unhealthy anxiety levels (Fleming, 2020). Vanbuskirk (2021) also mentioned that many learners have been struggling with remote learning and have been left behind. These children who did not flourish under distance learning have experienced a variety of academic, mental health, and physical effects.

Nonetheless, Barnum and Bryan (2020) have corroborated several factors affecting learners' engagement in remote learning. These were technology issues, responsibilities at home, including caring for siblings, stress from the pandemic, and a lack of interest in work that often went ungraded or didn't cover new material. Learners also adjust how they manage their time at home. According to Rinkema & Williams (2021), the pandemic has brought opportunities for learners to manage their time. Learners who are successful time managers are often successful, and it was never a burden for parents to scaffold their children. Meanwhile, learners who struggled to manage their time sometimes had extra difficulty.

However, due to poor time management, learners who had to multitask daily would have unfinished or unsatisfactory output. Learners should focus on successfully effectively completing a single task at a time to maximize productivity while learning (Sellers, 2020).

Learners' Coping Mechanisms in PMLM. Coping mechanisms are coping strategies that help to tolerate, minimize, and deal with difficult situations. According to Morin (2021), coping strategies should be chosen carefully because sometimes it's tempting to engage in strategies that will give quick relief but might create bigger problems. Thus, in choosing coping strategies, it is important to establish healthy coping skills that will help to reduce emotional stress. Nagar (2021) mentioned that the pandemic has increased stress and a higher emotional-oriented coping. In response, learners manifest their coping mechanisms, including avoiding difficult situations and solving problems. While the essence of learning inside the classroom and engaging in group activities are being missed, which could lead to stress for both teachers and learners, Chandra (2020) emphasized that low physical activity and spending all their time at home are creating negative impacts on learners which they try to overcome using a lot of other activities to cope with the situation.

In Poland, learners had difficulty coping upon shifting to online classes, which changed students' daily functioning. It is clearly shown that they were helpless and were experiencing difficulties in coping with the changes (Wirkus & Wirkus, 2021). This could mean that learners have not developed effective coping strategies for their struggles.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the Theory of Challenge and Support developed by Nevitt Sanford in 1966, which explains the importance of challenges and support systems that could be linked to learners' struggles and coping mechanisms.

According to Stanford (1966), a person needs a balanced amount of appropriate challenge and support to accomplish a certain task. To grow, a person must be ready physically and psychologically. The theory of challenge and support states that when a person is given too much support, they fail to learn. For example, when given too little support, people get frustrated by the challenges and quit. The theory best describes the present set-up where learners struggle to accomplish their learning tasks, adapt to the new learning environment, do multiple tasks, and manage time. Being new to modular distance learning, learners need to have support to face the many problems that emerged and are still emerging during modular instruction. The level of struggles the learners face need an equal level of coping mechanisms to accomplish the most essential learning competencies.

Challenges are continuously transpiring in the educational system. With the shifting of the educational system to other modes of learning, it is undeniable that learners are the most affected. Hence, they should be provided support to develop coping mechanisms. Learners need proper guidance in facing the new teaching mode's difficult circumstances. Teachers and parents should provide enough technical support or assistance so that learners can have meaningful learning experiences during this pandemic.

The struggles and coping mechanisms of learners in modular learning may vary significantly. For instance, some learners may struggle more with accomplishing the performance task while others struggle more with time management. Nonetheless, these struggles need to be addressed so that the implementation of modular learning becomes effective. Therefore, the concept of the Theory of Challenge and Support, that is, in every challenge, need to have support, can justify that struggles only need effective coping mechanisms. Since modular learning is still new for grade 6 learners, they have difficulties adopting this learning style at home. When learners are engaged in hard situations, they may develop a fear of failure. Or worse, they lose interest in learning. Thus, learners must know how to cope with those circumstances. Teachers, parents, and even friends can help every learner. Even if learners are studying at home, teachers still play an essential role in guiding them. With the pandemic still present, it is important to determine learners' struggles so that they can be provided with coping strategies to lessen their burden.

Conceptual Framework

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the learners' struggles and coping with printed modular learning modality in a district of a large-sized division in Central Philippines for the School Year 2021-2022.

Methodology:

This section presents the methodology of the study. It consists of the research design, respondents, data gathering instruments, the validity and reliability of the research instrument, data gathering procedures, analytical schemes, and statistical tools used in analyzing the data.

Research Design

The study used a mixed method research design, specifically Convergent Parallel Design, introduced by Criswell (2018), to determine the learner's struggles and coping in the printed modular learning modality. According to Criswell (2018), convergent mixed-method research design combines qualitative and quantitative methods to allow the researcher to integrate results. The design involves collecting both quantitative and qualitative data, which are then analyzed separately and brought together to draw conclusions and uncover relationships between the research questions. This research design requires a purposeful mixing of methods in data collection, data analysis, and interpretation of the evidence used to unveil in-depth knowledge of a situation that aims to identify the characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories.

The convergent mixed method research design is appropriate for this study as it gathers information about the characteristics within the present field of investigation. Determining the struggles of learners in modular learning requires qualitative analysis of information to arrive at a more tangible judgment. On the other hand, learners' level of coping needs quantitative analysis to draw conclusions and predict the outcome. The result needed to be quantified to make interpretations and inferences. The research objectives of this study are best attained with the convergent mixed-method research approach.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were 189 Grade 6 learners out of a total population of 371. The Cochran formula is used to calculate the ideal sample size. According to Briggs (2020), this test is appropriate in a situation with large populations to obtain the desired level of precision and confidence, and the desired proportion of the attributes present in the population. The sample of 189 learners was determined further through stratified random sampling so that all sections were equally represented. Stratified random sampling is one of four probability sampling techniques in which the total population is divided into homogenous groups (strata) to complete the sampling process (Kaplan, 2014). Using the proportion ratio of the population, the number of learners per stratum/section was determined and was finally selected through simple random sampling using the lottery method.

For the focused group discussions, 6 respondents were chosen which is composed of three (3) males and three (3) females. They were carefully chosen so that each of the other variables, monthly income, distance of home, and family size, will be represented.

Table 1 below shows the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1

Distribution of the Grade 6 Learner-Respondents

Schools	Population (N)	Sample (n)	Percentage (%)
A	10	5	2.65
B	18	9	4.76
C	12	6	3.17
D	40	20	10.58
E	26	13	6.88
F	25	13	6.88
G	23	12	6.35
H	25	13	6.88
I	12	6	3.17
J	34	17	9.00
K	23	12	6.35
L	55	28	14.81
M	8	4	2.12
N	11	6	3.17
O	49	25	13.23
TOTAL	371	189	100.00

Data Gathering Instrument

The questionnaire was a researcher-made instrument composed of three (3) parts. Part I of the questionnaire gathered information about the respondents' profile that describes learners' average family monthly income, the distance of home from school, sex, and size of family. Part II of the questionnaire determined the levels of coping of learners in adopting modular learning in the areas of accomplishing learning tasks, learning environment, multitasking activities, and time management. Each area has 8 items (or a total of 32), which were rated using a 5-point Likert scale where 5- Very High Level, 4- High Level, 3-Moderate Level, 2- Low Level, and 1- Very Low Level.

Part III determined the struggles of learners during the printed modular learning modality. This portion is administered through a focused group discussion (FGD) with the six (6) identified learners. This part has four (4) questions, which represent the struggles of learners in each area of the second variable. (1) What are some of the struggles you have encountered in accomplishing learning tasks in the printed modules? (2) What are the things that make you uncomfortable in your learning environment in the new normal? (3) What struggles have you encountered in attending to all your tasks? (4) What difficulties do you face in managing your time?

Validity

Validity explains how well the collected data covers the actual area of investigation, which means measuring what is intended to be measured (Taherdoost, 2016). According to Wong & Yamat (2020), when an instrument measures what it is supposed to measure, then the instrument is valid.

To ascertain the validity of the research instrument, it was checked by five (5) validators. To determine the validity of the research instrument, the researcher adopted the criteria developed for the evaluation of survey questionnaires set forth by Carter V. Good and Douglas E. Scates. The result of the validity was interpreted as Excellent (4.04 - 5.00), Very Good (3.28 - 4.03), Good (2.52 - 3.27), Fair (1.76 - 2.51), and Poor (1.00 - 1.75). The computed validity index of the instrument used in this study was 4.80, interpreted as excellent.

Reliability

Reliability refers to the measuring tool's stability and consistency over time (Surucu, 2020). Cronbach's Alpha was used to establish the reliability of the research instrument. According to Gelacio (2019), the Cronbach Alpha is used whenever the researcher has items that are not scored simply as right or wrong. Cronbach Alpha is a measure of internal consistency, that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group. It is considered to be a measure of scale reliability. A "high" value for alpha does not imply that the measure is unidimensional. The value of the test must be not less than 0.70 to 1.00 to be reliable (Taber, 2018). Reliability was established through a dry run with 30 Grade 6 learners who were non-respondents of the same district equally distributed by school, which 2 learners represented. The reliability index obtained by the research instrument of this study is 0.749 interpreted as acceptable.

Data Gathering Procedure

After establishing the validity and reliability of the instrument, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the survey. After the approval was sought, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the identified research respondents. Each respondent was provided with the survey questionnaire through the parents during the distribution of summative tests. The answered questionnaires were collected during the submission of the answered summative tests. Follow-ups were made through phone calls in case of failures to

return the completed questionnaire. Data was tabulated after the scores were collected to prepare them for statistical interpretation.

For the focus group discussion, the researcher asked the learners to share their personal struggles during the printed modular learning. Six (6) respondents were chosen and the respondents were three (3) males and three (3) females. They were carefully chosen so that each of the other variables, monthly income, distance of home, and family size, will be represented. From the start of the interview until the end, the interviews were recorded using two recorders. It helped the researcher to gather accurate data from the respondents. The answers provided by learners were interpreted by the researcher with the help of the adviser. The interpretations were consulted and reviewed by a language teacher, who is the district's English coordinator.

Finally, the researcher processed the gathered data using the Creswell convergent parallel procedure. The first phase was the analysis of the quantitative and qualitative data separately. Afterward, the results were merged to create the research body. This is done by comparing and contrasting the quantitative and qualitative results. The researcher then proceeded with the interpretation of the significant findings and, lastly, provided conclusions.

Research Ethics Protocol

This research paper strived to minimize the risk of harm to its target respondents by assuring them of the confidentiality of their responses and ensuring their anonymity throughout the entire research process. The researcher sought consent from the respondents' parents and assured them that no personal data compromising their identity was collected in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Likewise, all collected materials were appropriately disposed of by machine shredding or dissolved in water after the submission of the study. Soft copies of the data were deleted, leaving no chance of future retrieval. The protection of human subjects through the application of appropriate ethical principles is important in all research studies. In a qualitative study, ethical considerations have a particular resonance due to the in-depth nature of the study process (Arifin, 2018).

Analytical Schemes

The analytical schemes involved in this study were the following: descriptive, comparative, and thematic.

Objective No. 1, which aimed to establish the profile of the respondents in terms of average family monthly income, distance of home from school, sex, and size of family, used the descriptive analytical scheme.

Objective No. 2 sought to determine the level of coping of learners in printed modular learning modality in the areas of accomplishing learning tasks, learning environment, multitasking activities, and time management. It also used the descriptive analytical scheme.

Objective No. 3, which aimed to identify the level of coping of learners in printed modular learning modality when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables, employed the descriptive analytical scheme.

Objective No. 4, which sought to unfurl the significant difference in the levels of coping of learners in printed modular learning modality when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables, used the comparative analytical scheme.

Objective No. 5, which aimed to uncover the learner's struggles in the printed modular learning modality, used a descriptive-analytical scheme.

Statistical Tools

Results and Discussion:

Quantitative Findings

This part provides the quantitative findings of the research. This provides discussions on the significant numerical findings.

Table 2
Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower (Below Php10,000)	93	49.70
	Higher (Php10,000 and above)	94	50.30
Distance of Home From School	Nearer (Below 2 km)	84	44.90
	Farther (2 km and above)	103	55.10

Sex	Male	93	49.70
	Female	94	50.30
Family Size	Smaller (Below 5 members)	55	29.40
	Larger (5 members and more)	132	70.60
	Total	187	100.00

Table 2 shows the data on the profile of the respondents. As reflected in Table 93, 49.70 percent belonged to the lower category or with income lower than Php10,000, while 94 or 50.30 percent belonged to the higher category or with income higher than Php10,000. This implies that about half of the learners have less financial struggles. However, some of the learners need support to sustain their school needs. This does not align with the study of Albert et al. (2018), which illustrated that the majority of the family households in the Philippines belong to the lower class.

The table also shows that most learners live farther from school, with a frequency of 103 or 55.10 percent, while 44.90 percent, with a frequency of 84, live nearer to the school. This means that learners lived beyond 2 kilometers from the school, implying that many learners do not have easy access to school. With most schools situated in the upper barangays where there is a problem with transportation, the result could connote that many learners may have experienced difficulties in going to school and attending classes, as in the study of Bee (2019), most of the learners lived beyond 2 kilometer-radius from the school premises.

Meanwhile, it can be gleaned that the majority of the learners were female, with a frequency of 94 or 50.30 percent, compared to male learners, with a frequency of 93 or 49.70. This implies that education is not just for males but also for females. It may suggest that male and female children have equal opportunities in education. This is similar to the findings of Desoasido (2021), which revealed that learners had almost equal frequencies in terms of sex. He emphasized that such data is an advantage since it displays balance about the sexual roles of learners in school, thus strengthening gender equality.

Furthermore, there was a huge difference in the family size between smaller and larger categories. It is shown that the majority of the learners belonged to larger families with a frequency of 132 or 70.60 percent, while 55 or 29.40 belonged to the smaller family. This implies that many of the learners have siblings with whom they can bond. Having siblings is an advantage in distance learning because it only suggests that they have someone with whom they can work on their modular activities. The result confirms the study of Dumogho (2019) which showed that most of the respondents belonged to larger families.

Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality

Table 3 illustrates learners' coping level in printed modular learning modality, specifically in the areas of accomplishing learning tasks, learning environment, multi-tasking of activities, and time management.

Table 3

Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality in the Area of Accomplishing Learning Tasks

Items	Mean	Interpretation
I am doing my module while searching for more information on the internet.	2.88	Moderate Level
I use other learning materials available at home, such as books and notes.	3.61	High Level
I check the correctness of my answers through the key answers provided in the module.	3.33	Moderate Level
I ask for assistance from the teacher through phone calls.	2.20	Low Level
I talk to my parents or someone who could give me an explanation of what to do.	3.64	High Level
I ask my siblings for help in the learning tasks.	2.91	Moderate Level
I finish all learning tasks before the retrieval schedule.	3.93	High Level
I work on performance tasks by following the directions correctly.	3.79	High Level
Overall Mean	3.29	Moderate Level

As shown in the table, learners' coping level in printed modular learning modality in the area of accomplishing learning tasks is moderate, with an overall mean score of 3.29. It is inferred that the learners had been able to accomplish their learning tasks at home. It can be further seen from the table that item no. 7 on finishing all the learning tasks before the schedule of retrieval obtained the highest mean score of 3.93, interpreted as a high level. This suggests that the learners paid much attention to completing their modular activities prior to retrieval, which is also the time for submission. With that, the learners were able to cope with the different challenges in accomplishing all their learning tasks. Further, most of the learners were able to submit their learning tasks on time.

Nonetheless, item no. 4, asking for assistance from the teacher through phone calls, had the lowest mean score of 2.20, interpreted as a low level. This implies that the learners seldom ask for help from their teachers in

answering their activities through phone calls. Only a few learners consider their teachers to be the primary source of help during modular learning regarding answering the learning tasks.

The findings contradict the study of Yang et al. (2022), who revealed how important a teacher's assistance is to learners in this pandemic. They found out that learners who had adequate support from teachers and even parents had higher levels of engagement.

Table 4

Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality in the Area of Learning Environment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
I look for a good space at home to study.	4.05	High Level
I ask my parents to provide me with a study table or area.	3.09	Moderate Level
I keep my study area clean and comfortable.	4.00	High Level
I accept and understand the limitations of going to school due to the pandemic.	3.94	High Level
I avoid an area prone to noise and the crowd.	3.58	High Level
I engage myself in meaningful hands-on activities provided in the module.	3.47	Moderate Level
I make my study area comfortable.	3.83	High Level
I ensure that all materials needed are ready in my study area before starting the performance tasks.	3.85	High Level
Overall Mean	3.73	High Level

Table 4 reflects the level of coping of learners in printed modular learning modality in the area of the learning environment. As reflected in the table, learners' coping level in the learning environment was high, with an overall mean score of 3.73. This infers that the learners experience less serious problems with the type of learning environment they were in during the modular learning modality. In addition, their learning environment in the printed modular learning was able to meet their demands.

It can be seen that "item no. 3, which is on keeping their study area clean and comfortable," obtained the highest mean score of 4.00 or High Level. This infers that having a clean area for learning is one of the primary ways learners cope in terms of the learning environment during printed modular learning because it is comfortable for them to work in a clean environment. Furthermore, "item no. 2, which is on asking their parents to provide a study table or study area for them," had the lowest mean score of 3.09 or Moderate Level. The result suggests that the learners were working only on available learning spaces at their respective homes where they feel comfortable. Their parents' provision of study tables could have enhanced their comfort in studying.

This checks with the study of Kapasia et al. (2020), who revealed that one of the challenges encountered by learners in distance learning includes an unfavorable home learning environment. All conditions related to such were even aggravated when students were marginalized and from remote areas.

Table 5

Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality in the Area of Multitasking of Activities

Items	Mean	Interpretation
I follow the daily schedule provided by the school.	4.12	High Level
I make my daily routine of activities for studying.	3.66	High Level
I perform performance tasks while waiting for the availability of parents' help/assistance.	3.35	Moderate Level
I prioritize my modules over my house chores.	3.35	Moderate Level
I ask my parents or siblings to do the household chores while I am working on the modules.	3.20	Moderate Level
I avoid distractions and focus on things to be done.	3.56	High Level
I take a break to relax, like watching TV, eating, and playing.	3.34	Moderate Level
I tell my parents about the things that I cannot do alone to ask for assistance or consideration.	3.74	High Level
Overall Mean	3.54	High Level

Table 5 describes the level of coping of learners in printed modular learning in the area of multitasking activities. As reflected in the table, learners' overall coping in multitasking of module activities obtained an overall mean score of 3.54, interpreted as a high level. This could mean that the learners were able to cope with the different activities provided to them.

It can also be seen that item no. 1, on following the daily schedule provided by the school, obtained the highest mean score of 4.12, interpreted as a high level. The lowest mean score was obtained by item 5 on asking parents or siblings to do the household chores while working on the modules. This manifests in the learners diligently following the time frame or schedule of school to meet the deadline for outputs and work on other personal chores. Therefore, the learners are able to accomplish both their home chores and academic assignments because they are provided with schedules on when to do certain activities.

In addition, item no. 5, asking parents or siblings to do chores while the learner is working on the modules, obtained the lowest mean score of 3.20, interpreted Moderate Level. Learners are still working with the home tasks at home even if they are working with their module outputs. This means the learners had to do house chores even if they had modular tasks. Further, it can also mean that they were working with both house chores and modular tasks without asking the help of their parents or siblings. The finding could be similar to the study of Meniano and Tan (2022), who revealed that during distance learning, children experienced distractions that made them unable to focus. They emphasized that household chores were the major contributing factors to these issues.

Table 6
Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality in the Area of Time Management

Items	Mean	Interpretation
I plan ahead with the things I have to do.	4.02	High Level
I arrange my module from easy to difficult.	3.98	High Level
I answer my modules one by one or part by part.	3.88	High Level
I do learning tasks ahead.	3.91	High Level
I extend the time for difficult learning tasks.	3.71	High Level
I balance my time studying and having time to play and bond with my family.	3.83	High Level
I set my goal on a specific day.	3.87	High Level
I give enough time to complete my goal.	3.78	High Level
Overall Mean	3.88	High Level

Table 6 draws learners' coping level in printed modular learning in the area of time management. It can be gleaned from the table that the coping of learners in terms of time management during the printed modular learning was at a High Level, with an overall mean score of 3.88. This implies that the learners were able to manage their time during modular learning. They can use their time to accomplish modular tasks and personal and recreational activities.

The table also shows that planning ahead with the things to do in item no. 1 obtained the highest mean score of 4.02 or high level. This suggests that the learners manage their time by planning for future activities, such as accomplishing academic tasks and personal or recreational activities.

Nonetheless, it is reflected that extending the time for difficult learning tasks in item no. 5 had the lowest mean score of 3.71 or High Level. This suggests that students extended the time for difficult activities. However, it is the learners' least coping strategy for managing their time. It infers that they accomplish their modules on the given time, which could either be with the help of their parents or siblings or by their own understanding.

The finding supports the study of Fojtik (2018), who pointed out that distance learning is difficult for learners, especially in terms of the ability of the learner to plan a well-proportioned schedule for learning. It is difficult for them to spend extra time accomplishing difficult activities.

Summary

Area	Mean	Interpretation
Accomplishing Learning Task	3.29	Moderate Level
Learning Environment	3.73	High Level
Multitasking of Activities	3.54	High Level
Time Management	3.88	High Level
Overall mean	3.61	High Level

In summary of the aforementioned results, the overall coping level of learners is 3.61 or High Level. This infers that the learners are doing their best to cope with their various tasks in the printed modular learning modality. It has been reflected that the areas of Learning and Environment, Multitasking of Activities, and Time Management obtained high levels of coping with means of 3.73, 3.54, and 3.88, respectively.

Meanwhile, Accomplishing Learning Tasks obtained a mean of 3.29 or a moderate level. This shows that accomplishing learning tasks is where most learners find it hard to cope. It suggests that doing the modular tasks causes the learners to struggle more in this learning modality. It tells that printed modular learning is not advantageous for Grade 6 learners as performing tasks at home was more difficult for them to achieve.

This confirms the study of Dealagdon (2021), who discovered that the struggles of printed modular learning often came from difficulty understanding the module contents, which gave the learners a harder time accomplishing the provided tasks.

Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Table 7
Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality in the Area of Accomplishing Learning Tasks When Grouped According to Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation

I am doing my module while searching for more information on the internet.	2.91	Moderate Level	2.85	Moderate Level
I use other learning materials available at home, such as books and notes.	3.69	High Level	3.53	High Level
I check the correctness of my answers through the key answers provided in the module.	3.27	Moderate Level	3.38	Moderate Level
I ask for assistance from the teacher through phone calls.	2.34	Low Level	2.05	Low Level
I talk to my parents or someone who could explain to me what to do.	3.70	High Level	3.59	High Level
I ask my siblings for help in the learning tasks.	2.96	Moderate Level	2.86	Moderate Level
I finish all learning tasks before the retrieval schedule.	3.85	High Level	4.01	High Level
I work on performance tasks by following the directions correctly.	3.76	High Level	3.81	High Level
Overall Mean	3.34	Moderate Level	3.24	Moderate Level

Table 7 presents learners' coping levels in printed modular learning modality in the area of accomplishing learning tasks when they are grouped according to average family monthly income. The table shows that learners from lower and higher categories of average family income had moderate levels with an overall mean score of 3.34 in coping and accomplishing the learning tasks. It implies that learners from lower-income and higher-income families have the same experiences and problems in accomplishing tasks.

However, there was a huge disparity in the mean scores of item no. 4 on asking for assistance from the teacher through phone calls, where the lower group had a low level with a mean score of 2.34, and the higher group had a Low Level with a mean of 2.05. Though mean scores are both interpreted as low level, it can be noted that learners from families with higher income had numerically higher mean scores than their lower counterparts. This could imply that those from higher-income families were more likely to ask for assistance from their teachers, whereas those from lower-income families rarely call their teachers for help. This may be because they have less access to cell phones and other communication gadgets. This is analogous to Chen et al.'s study (2022), which revealed that higher-income families were more stressed in home learning environments. Furthermore, those from higher category income experienced more problems during remote learning, which could be why learners from this group are more likely to ask for help.

Table 8

Level of Coping of Learner' in Printed Modular Learning Modality in the Area of Learning Environment When Grouped According to Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
I look for a good space at home to study.	3.86	High Level	4.24	High Level
I ask my parents to provide me with a study table or area.	3.10	Moderate Level	3.09	Moderate Level
I keep my study area clean and comfortable.	3.91	High Level	4.09	High Level
I accept and understand the limitations of attending school due to the pandemic.	3.98	High Level	3.90	High Level
I avoid an area prone to noise and the crowd.	3.55	High Level	3.62	High Level
I engage myself in meaningful hands-on activities provided in the module.	3.53	High Level	3.41	Moderate Level
I make my study area comfortable.	3.65	High Level	4.01	High Level
I ensure that all materials needed are ready in my study area before starting the performance tasks.	3.68	High Level	4.02	High Level
Overall Mean	3.76	High Level	3.70	High Level

Table 8 presents learners' coping levels in printed modular learning modality in the learning environment when they are grouped according to average family monthly income. It can be seen from the table that both categories manifested a High Level of coping in terms of learning environment, with overall mean scores of 3.76 and 3.70. This suggests that learners from lower- and higher-income families have similar coping strategies to perform modular activities in their respective homes.

Nevertheless, item no. 1 displayed a notable difference in the mean scores between categories where the respondents from the lower family income group had a mean score of 3.86, interpreted as a high level, and the respondents from the higher family income group obtained a mean score of 4.24 also interpreted as high level. This is on looking for a good space at home to study. This implies that learners from higher-income families can look for comfortable spaces at home where they can answer their modules as compared to those learners in the lower family income category.

The finding aligns with that of Rodriguez-Planas (2020), who revealed that low-income learners were more likely to experience stress and struggles with distance learning. Furthermore, Bibon and Barcenas (2021) confirm that most families cannot provide or support the learners' academic needs.

Table 9

Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality in the Area of Multitasking of Activities When Grouped According to Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower	Interpretation	Higher	Interpretation
	Mean		Mean	
I follow the daily schedule provided by the school.	3.98	High Level	4.27	High Level
I make my daily routine of activities for studying.	3.59	High Level	3.72	High Level
I perform performance tasks while waiting for availability of parents' help/assistance.	3.42	Moderate Level	3.28	Moderate Level
I prioritize my modules over my house chores.	3.57	High Level	3.14	Moderate Level
I ask my parents or sibling to do the household chores while I am working on the modules.	3.26	Moderate Level	3.15	Moderate Level
I avoid distractions and focus on things to be done.	3.69	High Level	3.44	Moderate Level
I take a break to relax like watching TV, eating, and playing.	3.51	High Level	3.17	Moderate Level
I tell my parents on the things that I cannot do alone to ask assistance or considerations.	3.75	High Level	3.72	High Level
Overall Mean	3.57	High Level	3.52	High Level

Table 9 shows the level of coping of learners in printed modular learning modality in the area of multitasking of activities when grouped according to average family monthly income. As reflected on the table, lower and higher family income groups have high level of coping in terms of doing multiple tasks during modular learning with overall mean scores of 3.57 and 3.52, respectively. This infers that regardless of income, learners from both categories have almost similar routine in balancing their modular tasks and home chores.

Even so, it is reflected in item 1 which is, "I follow the daily schedule provided by the school" displayed a notable difference in the mean scores. It can be seen that lower income had 3.98 or High Level while those from the higher category had 4.27 or High Level. This shows that learners coming from higher-income families were more likely to follow the schedules given to them than their lower counterparts. This implies that those with high income parents have the luxury of time in accomplishing their modular activities as reflected in their schedules. It also means that they have lesser chores which could disrupt their schedule compared to their lower counterparts. In addition, it connotes that these learners were more likely to finish their module activities on time because they make it a priority task. Further, it tells that learners from lower income families may not work on modules when they have other tasks to do.

This contradicts the study of Bacolo et. al (2022) who revealed that learners' profile such as the family income has no link to learners' attitude. They suggest that the learners' behavior towards modular learning is not based on the socio-economic status of the family, but rather on personal motivation.

Table 10

Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality in the Area of Time Management When Grouped According to the Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower	Interpretation	Higher	Interpretation
	Mean		Mean	
I am doing my module while searching more information in the internet.	4.02	High Level	4.02	High Level
I use other learning materials available at home such as books and notes.	3.87	High Level	4.10	High Level
I check correctness of my answers through the key answer provided in the module.	3.80	High Level	3.97	High Level
I ask for assistance from the teacher through phone calls.	3.92	High Level	3.90	High Level
I talk to my parents or someone who can give me explanation on what to do.	3.66	High Level	3.76	High Level
I ask my siblings' help in the learning tasks.	3.90	High Level	3.76	High Level
I finish all learning tasks before the schedule of retrieval.	4.00	High Level	3.73	High Level
I work on performance tasks by following the directions correctly.	3.86	High Level	3.70	High Level

Overall Mean	3.94	High Level	3.82	High Level
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Table 10 shows the level of coping of learners in printed modular learning modality in the area of time management when grouped according to average monthly family income. It is shown that both the lower and higher categories had High Level of coping in terms of managing time in accomplishing tasks with the overall means of 3.94 and 3.82, respectively. It can be inferred that regardless of the family income, the learners have similar extent of coping mechanisms which have helped them manage their time and accomplish their tasks at home.

Meanwhile, item no. 7 on finishing all learning tasks before the schedule of retrieval had recorded a disparity in the mean scores where lower-income group obtained mean score of 4.00 and respondents with higher-income obtained mean score of 3.73. While both mean scores are interpreted high level this also means that learners coming from lower-income families are more likely to finish their learning activities before the deadline implying further that they exert more efforts in accomplishing their modular outputs before the schedule of retrieval.

This result is contrary to the findings of the study of Gutierrez (2021) which suggests that higher-income learners performed better in the modular distance learning. This implies that learners with much comfortable living have better accomplishment of outputs because they were provided with the necessary resources at home.

Table 11

Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality in the Area of Accomplishing Learning Tasks When Grouped According to Distance of Home from School

Items	Nearer		Farther	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
I am doing my module while searching more information in the internet.	3.08	Moderate Level	2.68	Moderate Level
I use other learning materials available at home such as books and notes.	3.70	High Level	2.72	Moderate Level
I check correctness of my answers through the key answer provided in the module.	3.29	Moderate Level	3.53	High Level
I ask for assistance from the teacher through phone calls.	2.24	Low Level	3.36	Moderate Level
I talk to my parents or someone who can give me explanation on what to do.	3.61	High Level	2.17	Low Level
I ask my siblings' help in the learning tasks.	2.85	Moderate Level	3.67	High Level
I finish all learning tasks before the schedule of retrieval.	3.99	High Level	2.96	Moderate Level
I work on performance tasks by following the directions correctly.	3.77	High Level	3.88	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.29	Moderate Level	3.80	High Level

Table 11 reflects the level of coping of learners in printed modular learning modality in the area of accomplishing learning tasks when grouped and compared according to distance of home from school.

As reflected on the table, the two categories had different levels of coping in terms of accomplishing the tasks. Respondents who live farther from home had obtained an overall mean score of 3.80 interpreted high level, while respondents who live nearer from home obtained an overall mean score of 3.29, interpreted moderate level. This means that learners residing farther from school were more concerned in accomplishing the tasks compared to those living nearer to school. Learners who live farther from school have given much attention in finishing their outputs for submission because distance might contribute to the delay of submission of learning tasks. Thus, they need to accomplish their learning earlier than the deadlines.

In the study of Oneye and Onyango (2021) it was also revealed that distance of residence was one of the hindrances of learners in a district in Tanzania. The farther the distance, the more stressful it is for the learners to go to school. Thus, they were less to perform tasks and activities compared to those who resides nearer in school. Further, they discussed the negative effects of distance to learners which includes being late, hunger due to travel, and tiredness which could impact their performance.

Table 12

Level of Coping of Learners in Printed Modular Learning Modality in the Area of Learning Environment When Grouped According to Distance of Home from School

Items	Nearer		Farther	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
I look for a good space at home to study.	4.06	High Level	4.05	High Level

I ask my parents to provide me a study table or study area.	3.19	Moderate Level	3.01	Moderate Level
I keep my study area clean and comfortable.	3.98	High Level	4.02	High Level
I accept and understand limitations of going to school due to pandemic.	3.99	High Level	3.90	High Level
I avoid an area prone to noise and the crowd.	3.63	High Level	3.54	High Level
I engage myself in meaningful hands-on activities provided in the module.	3.55	High Level	3.41	Moderate Level
I make my study area comfortable.	3.85	High Level	3.82	Moderate Level
I ensure that all materials needed are ready in my study area before starting the performance tasks.	3.68	High Level	3.99	High Level
Overall Mean	3.70	High Level	3.75	High Level

Table 12 shows the level of coping of learners in printed modular learning modality in the area of learning environment when grouped according to distance of home from school. It is shown that both categories had High Levels of coping in terms of learning environment with the overall means of 3.70 for the nearer category and 3.75 for the farther category. It tells that learners living either nearer or farther from the school have almost similar extent of coping regarding their learning spaces at home. This can also tell that the learning environment is almost in the same situations regardless of the learners' distance to school.

Furthermore, the item that was rated higher than the rest of the items by both groups of respondents was item no. 1 which states that "I look for a good space at home to study." This means that learners living farther from school were more likely to be prepared in terms of materials than their nearer counterparts. It implies that those living farther from school were more conscious of the completeness of needed materials before performing their tasks. This could be attributed to the fact that they also have difficult access to stores where they can buy the needed resources for their performance tasks.

This is contrary to the study of Baliyan and Khama (2020) where it was revealed that distance to school has significant impact on their academic achievement. Further, their Post Hoc analysis revealed that long travelling distance had negative impact on the learner's academic performance. They stressed that those living nearer were more prepared in school than those living farther because they spent more time with travel. Thus, they recommend that learners stay closer to school and have reliable school transportation.

Conclusion:

The study found that most learners in the printed modular learning modality (PMLM) come from higher-income families, live far from school, are female, and belong to larger households. Overall, learners demonstrated a high level of coping with PMLM, particularly in learning environment, multitasking, and time management, while coping with accomplishing learning tasks was moderate, except for those living farther from school who coped better. No significant differences in coping were observed across the variables studied. Key struggles included difficulty with independent learning, distractions at home, multiple tasks, and unguided activity schedules, with the main challenge being learners' inability to complete modular tasks independently. Despite these challenges, learners' coping mechanisms helped them manage. The study recommends providing parent education to support learners at home, limiting costly activities, encouraging parental communication through calls or group chats, setting up accessible drop boxes for module submission, monitoring learner progress with enrichment activities, involving parents in school evaluations to address challenges, and reminding parents that home functions as the new school during weekdays. Further research is also advised to enhance PMLM implementation, given its ongoing relevance during health crises in Philippine public schools.

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